

MATERIALS FOR TEACHING CULTURE: REALIA, FILMS, SIGNS

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Abstract: *The culture of teaching and learning refers to the beliefs and value system in which both educators and learners value the process of teaching and learning, where their practices reflect their commitment and where the resources to facilitate teaching and learning are made available.*

Key words: *realia, movie, films, signs, symbol, cultural symbols, emblems, hand gestures, flags, animals.*

Custom is an inherited stereotypical way of behavior, which is reproduced in a particular society or social group and is familiar to their members. Tradition is a set of representations, rituals, habits and skills of practical and social activity, being transmitted from generation to generation, which are the regulators of social relations. B) household culture (everyday life). C) daily behavior, which includes not only the rules of behavior and etiquette, but also facial expressions, gestures. D) “national picture of the world”, showing the peculiarities of thinking and perception of the world. In education, realia (/ri'eɪ, li, ə/ pron. Ree-ay-lee-ah) are objects from real life used in classroom instruction by educators to improve students' understanding of other cultures and real-life situations. A teacher of a foreign language often employs realia to strengthen students' associations between words for common objects and the objects themselves. In many cases, these objects are part of an instructional kit that includes a manual and is thus considered as being part of a documentary whole by librarians. In translation, Realia (plural

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given era. Just as movies reflect the anxieties, beliefs, and values of the cultures that produce them, they also help to shape and solidify a culture's beliefs. Sometimes the influence is trivial, as in the case of fashion trends or figures of speech. After the release of Flashdance in 1983, for instance, torn T-shirts and leg warmers became hallmarks of the fashion of the 1980s (Pemberton-Sikes, 2006). However, sometimes the impact can be profound, leading to social or political reform, or the shaping of ideologies. During the 1890s and up until about 1920, American culture experienced a period of rapid industrialization. As people moved from farms to centers of industrial production, urban areas began to hold larger and larger concentrations of the population. At the same time, film and other methods of mass communication (advertising and radio) developed, whose messages concerning tastes, desires, customs, speech, and behavior spread from these population centers to outlying areas across the country. The effect of early mass-communication media was to wear away regional differences and create a more homogenized, standardized culture. Film played a key role in this development, as viewers began to imitate the speech, dress, and behavior of their common heroes on the silver screen (Mintz, 2007). In 1911, the Vitagraph company began publishing The Motion Picture Magazine, America's first fan magazine. Originally conceived as a marketing tool to keep audiences interested in Vitagraph's pictures and major actors, The Motion Picture Magazine helped create the concept of the film star in the American imagination. Fans became obsessed with the off-screen lives of their favorite celebrities, like Pearl White, Florence Lawrence, and Mary Pickford (Doyle, 2008).

Cultural symbols can be religious or spiritual, or they can represent the ideology or philosophy of a culture's language, values and traditions. Cultural

of a particular group of people. The Christian culture has the cultural symbol of the cross, where the Jewish culture has the cultural symbol of the Star of David. Cultural symbols don't have to be actual symbols or signs; they can also be gestures such as hand shakes and hand signals. Additionally, the same symbol can mean different things in different cultures. Americans should be careful in Greece, for example. The thumbs up, which symbolizes that everything is great in American culture, is just like giving the middle finger in Greek culture

References:

1. Jean-Pierre Berwald. 1987. Teaching Foreign Language with Realia and other Authentic Materials. Eric. Center for applied linguistics. Washington. Autumn 2004 Smith, B (1997) •
2. Мусина, Н. М. Realia as a cultural phenomenon / Н. М. Мусина. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2017. — № 22 (156). — С. 481- 484. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/156/43949/> (дата обращения: 16.04.2023).
3. Khakimov, S. R., & Sharopov, B. K. (2023). Educational Quality Improvement Events Based on Exhibition Materials in Practical Training Lessons. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education*, 1(2), 5-10.
4. Yuvmitov, A., & Hakimov, S. R. (2021). Influence of seismic isolation on the stress-strain state of buildings. *Acta of Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent*, 11(1), 71-79.
5. Шаропов, Б. Х., Хакимов, С. Р., & Рахимова, С. (2021). Оптимизация режимов гелиотеплохимической обработки золоцементных композиций. *Матрица научного познания*, (12-1), 115-123.

6. Ювмитов, А. С., & Хакимов, С. Р. (2020). ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ СЕЙСМОИЗОЛЯЦИИ НА ДИНАМИЧЕСКИЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ЗДАНИЯ. *Acta of Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent*, 10(2), 14.
7. Hakimov, S., & Dadaxanov, F. (2022). STATE OF HEAT CONDUCTIVITY OF WALLS OF RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS. *Science and innovation*, 1(C7), 223-226.
8. Yuldashev, S., & Hakimov, S. (2022). ТЕМИР ЙЎЛ ТРАНСПОРТИДАН КЕЛИБ ЧИҚАДИГАН ТЕБРАНИШЛАР ҲАҚИДА. *Science and innovation*, 1(A5), 376-379
9. Хакимов, С. (2022). АКТИВ ВА ПАССИВ СЕЙСМИК УСУЛЛАРИ ҲАМДА УЛАРНИНГ АСОСИЙ ВАЗИФАЛАРИ. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(2), 30-36.